

An FDA Guide on Indications for Use and Device Reporting of Artificial Intelligence-Enabled Devices: Significance for Pediatric Use

KEY POINTS

1. Medical devices, including software as a medical device (SaMD) incorporating artificial intelligence, are cleared for sale and marketing by the Food and Drug Administration (FDA).
2. The FDA clears devices based upon a specific *indications for use (IFU)*.
3. Performance of the device in the premarket submission must support the indication(s) for use.
4. If information on the pediatric applicability of a device is not clear from either the indications for use or the summary of performance data, users are encouraged to contact the device vendor to clarify whether information on the performance of the device in pediatric patients is available.
5. Reporting of known or suspected device failures is an important way to provide feedback about a device to both the manufacturer and the Food and Drug Administration (FDA).

INTRODUCTION: ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE AS A DEVICE IN RADIOLOGY

Devices incorporating artificial intelligence (AI) and machine learning (ML) can be found in many areas of medicine, and radiology has been a pioneer in adopting AI-enabled devices into the clinic. The FDA list of cleared devices that include AI/ML technology is dominated by radiology.¹ However, the American College of Radiology (ACR) reported in its first annual survey of clinical artificial intelligence usage that 94% of AI users experienced inconsistent device performance. Most of these inconsistencies were reported as being due to variability across patient groups seen by the device.²

The majority of these devices were reviewed and cleared by FDA for a specific indications for use. Thus, one possible explanation for this inconsistent performance is that the devices were unknowingly used in a patient group or manor outside of the cleared indications. Understanding indications for use may help bridge this gap in understanding and better support consistent device usage and performance. Pediatric patients are of particular concern as most medical devices designed for adults are eventually used on children. As data-driven AI devices become more prevalent, if these devices are not specifically designed for pediatric patients, then their safety and efficacy in these patients remain unclear. We provide a brief guide for practicing radiologists and device users on the FDA clearance and premarket evaluation process. Further emphasis is given on understanding pediatric indications and what to do if they are not explicitly given and the important role device users have in postmarket device monitoring to report issues regarding device safety and efficacy.

510(K) PREMARKET NOTIFICATION AND INDICATIONS FOR USE

The FDA regulates firms that manufacture, repackage, re-label, and/or import medical devices sold for clinical use in the United States. (It should be noted that there are situations in which AI can be developed and deployed clinically without FDA authorization, such as is done locally in some institutions). Thus, the scope of this discussion is limited to FDA cleared devices. The FDA takes a risk-based approach to medical device regulation. Medical devices are placed in one of three device classes (Class I, Class II, and Class III) based on the level of regulatory control necessary to provide a reasonable assurance of safety and effectiveness. Class I devices are considered lowest risk, and Class III devices the highest.

39 Most radiological imaging and therapeutic devices marketed in the US are FDA class II medical devices
40 subject to the 510(k) Premarket Notification process³ which determines if a new device is substantially
41 equivalent to a legally marketed predicate device.⁴

42 Devices are cleared by FDA for a specific indications for use, which describes the general purpose of the
43 device and the disease or condition the device will diagnose or treat, including a description of the
44 intended patient population.³ The performance data needed to support a premarket submission depends
45 on both the IFU of the device and the device technology. Performance data is used to ensure that the
46 safety and effectiveness are equivalent to the existing technology.

47 Many imaging and image processing devices have a very general IFU that broadly cover large patient
48 populations. This makes the device accessible to the largest number of patients. However, determining
49 whether a particular device has been specifically evaluated for use in pediatric patients can be
50 challenging in these situations. Figure 1 provides three examples of previously cleared IFUs that include
51 varying degrees of detail on the pediatric population for which the device is intended to be used. Fig. 1a
52 illustrates how to find the IFU from the public summary in the FDA 510k database
53 (<https://www.accessdata.fda.gov/scripts/cdrh/cfdocs/cfpmn/pmn.cfm>). The IFU in Fig. 1a describes a
54 device specifically intended for neonates and infants ages 0 to 12 months. Fig. 1b is more general,
55 stating that adult and pediatric images can be processed by the device, whereas Fig. 1c makes no
56 mention of the indicated patient population. In these instances, users can refer to the summary of how
57 the device was evaluated in the 510k summary or the device user manual to determine what patient
58 subgroups were included in evaluations.

59 If pediatric performance data is not clear in either of these documents, users are encouraged to contact
60 the device vendor to clarify whether information on the performance of the device in pediatric patients
61 is available. Recently, the FDA has focused on ensuring transparency about the validation of AI-enabled
62 devices, especially regarding inclusion of pediatric data. As transparency improves in public summaries,
63 users are encouraged to follow these steps described above and summarized in Figure 2.

a)

1. 510(k) Premarket Notification

2. Device Classification Name automated radiological image processing software
510(k) Number K200356
Device Name MEDO ARIA
Applicant Medo Ai
4560 TEC Centre, 10230 Jasper Avenue
Edmonton, CA T5J4p6
Applicant Contact Dornmoosh Zonoobi
Correspondent Medo Ai
32 Carpenter Street
SG 059911
Correspondent Contact Dornmoosh Zonoobi
Regulation Number 892.2050
Classification Product Code QIH
Date Received 02/13/2020
Decision Date 06/11/2020
Decision Substantially Equivalent (SESE)
Regulation Medical Specialty Radiology
510k Review Panel Radiology
Summary Summary
Type Traditional
Reviewed by Third Party No
Combination Product No

3. DEPARTMENT OF HEALTH AND HUMAN SERVICES
Food and Drug Administration
Indications for Use
Form Approved: OMB No. 0910-0120
Expiration Date: 06/30/2020
See PRA Statement below.

510(k) Number (if known)
K200356

Device Name
MEDO ARIA

Indications for Use (Describe)
MEDO ARIA is designed to view and quantify ultrasound image data using machine learning techniques to aid trained medical professionals in diagnosis of developmental dysplasia of the hip (DDH). The device is intended to be used on neonates and infants, aged 0 to 12 months.

b)

510(k) Number (if known)
K213307

Device Name
Eclipse II with Smart Noise Cancellation

Indications for Use (Describe)
The software performs digital enhancement of a radiographic image generated by an x-ray device. The software can be used to process adult and pediatric x-ray images. This excludes mammography applications.

c)

510(k) Number (if known)
K201039

Device Name
HepaFat-AI

Indications for Use (Describe)
HepaFat-AI is indicated to:

- Assess the volumetric liver fat fraction, proton density fat fraction and steatosis grade in individuals with confirmed or suspected fatty liver disease;

When interpreted by a trained physician, the results can be used to

- monitor liver fat content in patients undergoing weight loss management and can be used to
- aid in the assessment and screening of living donors for liver transplant.

64

65 **Figure 1 Finding the indications for use (IFU) using the FDA 510(k) database:**
 66 <https://www.accessdata.fda.gov/scripts/cdrh/cfdocs/cfpmn/pmn.cfm> with three example IFUs. a) Finding a 510k summary
 67 using the 510k database starting with 1. searching for the product, 2. selecting the “Summary” hyperlink in the database
 68 entry. 3. The IFU is found in the summary document. This IFU is an example where pediatric patients with a specific age
 69 range are indicated. b) and c) are further examples from products where pediatric patients are mentioned more broadly in
 70 the indications or not at all.

71

72 **Figure 2 Locating pediatric performance data. Starting with the indications for use, users can also check for performance data**
 73 **in the device [510k summary](#), user manual, or ask the vendor.**

74 **Off-Label Use**

75 Off-label use describes the situation where a device is used outside of its indications for use. Off-label use
 76 is considered a practice of medicine decision that is not regulated by FDA. A medical professional may use
 77 a device off-label based on their best medical judgement and at their own risk.⁴ Off-label use of medical
 78 devices in the context of pediatric patients has been previously discussed,⁵ as the majority of cleared or
 79 approved devices do not include specific pediatric indications. To the best of these authors' knowledge, a
 80 discussion focusing on the off-label use of AI-enabled device in pediatric patients has not previously
 81 occurred. As it is generally accepted that AI solutions behave unpredictably when applied to data
 82 characteristically different than their training populations, additional analysis by multiple stakeholders
 83 would be helpful to understand the implications of off-label use of AI-enabled device technology in
 84 pediatric patients.

85 **ADVERSE EVENTS AND FDA MEDICAL DEVICE REPORTING**

86 After devices are cleared for clinical use, they will be exposed to larger populations of patients over longer
 87 time periods than originally tested. Imaging professionals, including radiologists, play an important role in
 88 promoting the safety of medical devices by reporting to the FDA and device manufacturers when devices
 89 malfunction. Medical Device Reporting (MDR) is used by the FDA for postmarket monitoring and
 90 encompasses several mechanisms for reporting events depending on their severity.⁶ Reports to the FDA
 91 inform the potential recall of marketed devices, aid in premarket device review, and inform other users
 92 of potential device problems.

93 Device manufacturers must report events that may have caused or contributed to the death or serious
 94 injury of a patient as well as device malfunctions that, if they were to occur again, would be likely to cause
 95 or contribute to death or serious injury within 30 calendar days of becoming aware of the event.

96 User facilities must report device adverse events that contributed to the death or serious injury of a
 97 patient, within 10 working days via the FDA Form 3500. FDA also accepts voluntary reports from patients
 98 and consumers who wish to alert the FDA to a medical device problem. (It is not uncommon for FDA to
 99 receive multiple adverse event reports for the same incident). These reporting forms ask for patient
 100 information, as well as information about the incident, the suspected device, and the reporter. Reports
 101 providing feedback on device performance can be reported from individual incidents or summarized
 102 retrospectively. Providing more information about potential safety or efficacy concerns regarding FDA
 103 regulated products can better inform a timely response and aid other device users in preempting similar
 104 issues. Redacted reports are freely available via FDA's Manufacturer and User Facility Device Experience

105 (MAUDE) database. Reporting forms and related information, including how to subscribe to notifications
106 of device safety alerts, can be found at: <https://www.fda.gov/safety/medwatch>.

107 CONCLUSIONS

108 Medical devices are cleared for specific indications for use, and the performance data evaluated during
109 the premarket submission support the indications for use. Understanding the indications for use of a given
110 device—including the patient population in which the device is intended to be used—is critical to ensuring
111 that the device performs as expected. Problems with devices are monitored primarily through a passive
112 reporting system of failures and patient injuries. Thus, it is crucial that radiologists and users know how
113 to access and utilize tools for determining indications for use and reporting systems to provide a stronger
114 foundation for informed use of medical devices for patients of all ages.

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118 [samd/artificial-intelligence-and-machine-learning-aiml-enabled-medical-devices](https://www.fda.gov/medical-devices/software-medical-device-samd/artificial-intelligence-and-machine-learning-aiml-enabled-medical-devices)
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